

FPGA BASED LOW LATENCY, LOW POWER STREAM PROCESSING AI

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Motivation

nearest neighbor

neural network

support vector machine

etc. ...

recurrent neural network

1D-CNN

“heart attack”

convolutional neural network

“cat”

Motivation

- Wanted:
 - high throughput
 - ⚡ limited mainly by data access bandwidth
 - power efficiency
 - ⚡ limited mainly by data access cost
 - radiation hardness
 - ⚡ limited mainly by weak sequential cells

➔ limited mainly by memory!!!

do we need memory?

How to build simple NN without memory?

$$\text{1D-Convolution: } y_f(t) = \max \left(0, \sum_{c=0}^{C-1} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} w_{i,c,f} \cdot x_c(t - i \cdot \Delta t) + b_f \right)$$

Step 1: Quantization

Step 2: Convolution

Step 3: Reducing the input count

Step 4: Precompute multiplication

$$y = \max\left(0, \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} w_i \cdot x_i + b\right)$$

$$w_0 = 0.43, w_1 = -0.24$$

$$w_2 = 0.65, b = 0.44$$

x_0	x_1	x_2	y	$ y $		x	y
0	0	0	0.44	0		0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0
0	0	1	1.09	1		0 0 0 0 0 1	0 1
0	0	2	1.74	2		0 0 0 0 1 0	1 0
0	0	3	2.39	2		0 0 0 0 1 1	1 0
0	1	0	0.2	0		0 0 0 1 0 0	0 0
0	1	1	0.85	1		0 0 0 1 0 1	0 1
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮			
1	0	0	0.87	1		0 1 0 0 0 0	0 1
1	0	1	1.52	2		0 1 0 0 0 1	1 0
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮			
3	3	2	2.31	2		1 1 1 1 1 0	1 0
3	3	3	2.96	3		1 1 1 1 1 1	1 1

ASIC:

$$y_0 = x_0 \cap (\overline{x_1} \cup x_4) \cup \overline{x_3} \cap (x_5 \cup x_6) \cup \dots$$

$$y_1 = \dots$$

FPGA:

$$y_0 = LUT(x_0, x_1, \dots)$$

$$y_1 = LUT(x_0, x_1, \dots)$$

Step 5: Pooling

Results

- All activations are quantized and stored in registers
 - quick, efficient and radiation hard
- All weights and biases are still floating values and implicitly coded into the Boolean functions
 - better training
- No RAM access needed at all
- Each neuron is explicitly and exclusively implemented
 - ~300 transistors per neuron in ASIC
 - ~10 LUTs per neuron in FPGA
- But:
 - it is not possible to retrain ASIC (needs reproduction → \$)
 - FPGA can be retrained, but it contains 5T SRAM cells → radiation)

Flow automation

Evaluation

- Spartan 7 S15
- 2155 LUT (26%)
- 26nJ per sample (full inference)
- 10MHz input sample rate

Conclusion

- The method has some fundamental limitations
 - low bitwidth
 - low synapse count
 - 1 dimensional convolution
- Within those limitations, it outperforms any other methodology
- An ASIC solution would improve performance and efficiency by at least an order of magnitude

The OCTOPUS project idea

1. Develop an analogue frontend chip
2. Improve the methodology
3. Medical application
4. Industry application

1 Develop an analogue frontend chip

2 Extend the methodology

available

Conv1D	quantization while training
Max Pooling 1D	depthwise separation
Dense	
Global average pooling	ReLU

planned

Conv2D	width&height-wise separation
other std. activation	
nonlinear tensor functions	

$$y = \max \left(0, \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} v_i \cdot x_i^2 + w_i \cdot x_i + b \right)$$

3 Health application

- Use the system as is to detect blood pressure
 - determine blood speed by following the pressure peaks

4 Railway application

- Measure the sound (in air or in metal) of a train passing
- use on sensor AI to detect
 - axle traversing
 - weight (load) per axle
 - speed of train
 - type of train
- carefully!!! design and verify a system which uses unreliable AI components in a safety critical system
 - decide if the track is free based on our system's "best guess"